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**THE RIGHT TO GOOD GOVERNANCE AND ENSURING CHILDREN'S RIGHTS
IN THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN: THEORETICAL AND
PRACTICAL ISSUES OF INTERACTION**

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Summary. *In the article, the theoretical and practical issues of interaction in the field of good governance and the provision of children's rights in the Republic of Azerbaijan are analyzed in an extensive manner. It is noted that the right to good governance is a fundamental right because it requires authorities to comply with a certain standard of behavior based on the rule of law. The right to good governance differs from "classic" fundamental rights. In the classical sense, the realization of basic rights is based on the non-interference of the state in people's lives and activities, and the right to good governance is based on the legitimate activity of states. The elements of the right to good governance are mainly: the right to appeal; a fair and impartial approach; consideration of cases in a reasonable time; to be heard and receive legal assistance in general; freedom of access to information. As constitutional norms that include these elements, Article 60 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan entitled "Administrative and judicial guarantee of rights and freedoms", Article 61 "The right to receive legal assistance", Article 32 "The right to privacy", Article 57 "The right to appeal" can be mentioned in this context. In the end, with the conducted analyses, we come to the conclusion that in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the right to good governance and mutual action in the direction of ensuring children's rights have been determined in several directions: ensuring human rights as a whole; establishing the right to good governance in domestic legislation; ensuring the right to good governance for children's rights; coordinating the activities of state bodies on ensuring the right to good governance; implementation of cooperation within the framework of international organizations and international agreements on the development of good governance law; implementation of relevant improvements and developments in this area.*

Keywords. *the right to good governance, right to appeal, fair and impartial approach, ensuring human rights and freedoms, international treaties, national legislative acts, children's rights.*

One of the rights guaranteed by the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union is the right to good governance. The essence of this right is that every person has the right to have his/her case reviewed by the institutions and bodies of the Union in an impartial, fair and reasonable time. The recognition and normative determination of the right to good governance in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the draft constitution of the European Union was a high achievement in the development of the right of citizen participation in the management of state affairs. Article 41 of the Charter is based on case law, which establishes various principles of good governance. In addition, the right to good governance is usually viewed not as a subjective right, but as a category of rights [8, p. 324-326]. Thus, the establishment of the right to good governance means the emergence of a new fundamental right. It is the only right

enshrined in Chapter V of the Charter, which applies to "every person" in contact with the institutions and bodies of the Union, and incorporates these elements:

- the right of everyone to have their case reviewed by the institutions and bodies of the Union impartially, fairly, and within a reasonable time;
- the right of everyone to demand compensation for damage caused by Union institutions or their employees during the performance of their duties in accordance with the general principles of the legislation of the member states;
- The right of every person to communicate in one of the official languages of the agreements with the institutions of the Union;
- the duty of the administration to justify its decisions.

Overall, the main distinguishing feature of the Charter is its unique classification of fundamental human rights and freedoms. Thus, the Charter, which consists of 7 sections and 54 articles, has systematized basic human rights and freedoms in a unique way. The basis of the classification is not subjective rights (personal, political, economic, etc.), but values aimed at their protection: human dignity; freedom; equality; solidarity [1, p. 266]. It is noted in the legal literature that even if the full content of this right is not reflected in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, the main provisions are defined in this area [7, p. 24-25; 9, p. 244].

Thus, the right to good governance is a fundamental right because it requires authorities to adhere to a certain standard of behavior based on the rule of law towards citizens. The right to good governance differs from "classic" fundamental rights. The point is that in the realization of basic rights in the classical sense, the state does not interfere in people's lives and activities, while the right of good governance is based on the lawful activity of states.

In addition, the preamble of the Charter states that the Union should be established based not only on the indivisible, universal values of human dignity, freedom, equality, and solidarity, but also on the principles of democracy, the rule of law, and good governance. In addition, Article 8 of the Treaty of Lisbon states that in all its activities, the European Union observes the principle of equality of its citizens, who enjoy equal opportunities by its administrations, bodies, and institutions. The importance of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union for determining administrative principles is justified by three specific provisions: the right to good administration (Article 41); the right of access to documents (Article 42); the right to appeal to the ombudsman (Article 43). In addition, many other rights affect administrative behavior and structures and constitute the content of "good governance". Among such rights, the following should be mentioned in particular: the right to petition the European Parliament (Article 44); the right to protection of personal data (Article 8); equality before the law (Article 20); non-discrimination (Article 21); The right to cultural, religious

and linguistic diversity in the European Union (Article 22); equality between men and women (Article 23); access to services of general economic interest (Article 36); the right to an effective remedy and a fair trial (Article 47).

Thus, the right to good management is a set of specific powers defined for the performance of specific tasks for a certain administrative body, and accordingly, the state requires appropriate behavior from the body to which it has given these powers, under certain conditions, within the framework of the concept of good management. This right, which has a complex nature, has been concretely established for the first time in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and has essentially emerged in the direction of the realization of the concept of good governance and has been formed as a subjective human right that has found its normative approval in international and domestic legal acts. The right to good governance in relation to the legal space of the European Union, as one of the basic rights of the citizens of the European Union, is aimed at preventing the bodies and institutions of the Union from making unbiased, legal, and unreasonable decisions, and considering the affairs of the citizens of the European Union in a timely and efficient manner, in accordance with the law. At the same time, this right is accompanied by the obligation of European Union bodies and institutions, as well as all officials working in these bodies, to properly and appropriately deal with the affairs of citizens in accordance with the law.

In modern times, important reforms are being carried out in the legal, social, administrative, and economic spheres in the Republic of Azerbaijan. In the management sphere, the most optimal and effective mechanisms, criteria such as "transparency" and "trust" in relations between citizens and the state are highlighted. Against the background of these processes, the use of European practice, which has already gained experience in the sphere of application of good governance law, and the application of this experience both in legislation and in the activities of state bodies, are both relevant and necessary. According to Article 12 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, human and civil rights and freedoms, which are defined as the supreme goal of the state, are applied in accordance with the international agreements supported by the Republic of Azerbaijan. At the current stage of development, the Republic of Azerbaijan is trying to actively cooperate with the member states of the European Union and integrate into a single pan-European legal space. In this regard, the adaptation of the legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the practice of law enforcement to European standards is one of the most important problems in the sphere of good governance as a mechanism for the protection of human rights.

Public administration does not consist only of relations between state structures. Issues such as openness of power, transparency of decisions, and participation of the local population in the decision-making mechanism are

directly related to that area [4, p. 12-15]. During the last years, certain works on the reform of the civil service have been carried out in the Republic of Azerbaijan, and the legislative base has been strengthened for this purpose. Among the laws in force in this sphere, the Laws on Civil Service; on administrative proceedings; on the fight against corruption; on consideration of citizens' appeals; on the rules of ethical behavior of civil servants; on obtaining information; on the procedure for citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan to use the right of legislative initiative, etc. should be emphasized in particular.

In addition to the laws, the decrees and orders of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan serve to modernize public administration based on the requirements of the right to good governance, and the following legislative acts adopted in this direction should be especially noted: Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the approval of the National Strategy for increasing transparency and fighting corruption (28.07.2007); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the approval of the Regulation on disclosure of acts of state and local self-government bodies through electronic information systems (16.02.2011); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the establishment of the State Agency for Public Service and Social Innovations under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan (13.07.2012); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on approval of the Development Concept "Azerbaijan 2020: Vision of the Future" (29.12.2012); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the Rules for the use of a single electronic information system for citizens' appeals in local executive authorities (29.04.2015); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on some measures in the field of increasing transparency in the provision of public services, electronicization of registration and licensing procedures by place of residence (31.08.2015); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on additional measures related to the improvement of management in the areas of population employment, labor, social protection and security (09.08.2018); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the electronicization of internal management processes in state bodies (institutions) (27.10.2018); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on additional measures related to the optimization of the structure and improvement of management of a number of state bodies in the Republic of Azerbaijan (17.01.2019); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on additional measures related to the improvement of management in the field of social protection (30.12.2019); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on expanding the application of electronic services in the field of state registration of civil status acts (23.09.2020); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on some measures related to the improvement of management in the field of digitization,

innovation, high technologies and communication in the Republic of Azerbaijan (11.10.2021); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on improving management in the field of state support for the development of entrepreneurship (11.10.2021); Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on some measures related to the improvement of management in the field of science and education in the Republic of Azerbaijan (28.06.2022), etc.

Although the right to good governance in the Republic of Azerbaijan is not established in any legislative action in the form of a separate article, if we take it as a whole, it is possible to find all the elements of this right in the national legislation. The main elements of the right to good governance are the right to appeal; a fair and impartial approach; consideration of cases in a reasonable time; to be heard and receive legal assistance in general; freedom of access to information. As constitutional norms that include these elements, Article 60 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan entitled "Administrative and judicial guarantee of rights and freedoms", Article 61 "The right to receive legal assistance", Article 32 "The right to privacy", Article 57 "The right to appeal" can be mentioned in this context [10].

In addition, the creation of the Good Governance Council under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan has been proposed too. It has also been recommended to include some matters such as demonstration of political will to state bodies in improving governance; development of management recommendations for public bodies based on good management principles; constant monitoring of the situation related to the implementation of good management principles in state bodies; analysis of the results of the evaluation of the quality of public administration in the Republic of Azerbaijan by local and international (including representing world financial institutions) research groups in the functions of such a Council.

In terms of ensuring good governance, it is very important to establish the necessary level of transparency, accountability, and citizen participation in the legislation. Otherwise, there are ample opportunities for corruption and general misappropriation or inefficient use of national resources. The factors that create these opportunities have certain features such as, first of all, not providing or confusing a number of relevant legal concepts in legal acts, imprecise determination of the status of legal and natural persons, and not providing appropriate operating procedures of state bodies, organizations, and employees, repetition of various legal norms in meanings different from those established in society and other legislative acts, etc.

In our opinion, one of the ways to improve public administration on the basis of the right to good governance is the wide use of electronic resources, the possibilities of information and communication technologies in the public services

provided to the population, and the development of electronic state-building in general. This can be considered an inevitable requirement of the modern era. With the emergence of the concept of the electronic state, an adaptation of public administration to information society technologies takes place, the electronic state performs the role of a reforming tool in public administration. The technologies of the information society themselves act as a tool for the modernization of state administration. In addition, many developing countries have identified the possibility of approaching the standard of living in developed countries through the implementation of e-government. However, despite the necessary work being done in the sphere of the formation of the electronic state, neither the globalization process, nor the effective development of the information society, nor the mass application and realization of the electronic state concept are possible without the elimination of information inequality [5, p. 36]. As a whole, certain tasks such as implementation of effective, transparent, and controllable state management and local self-government in national strategies and state programs related to the establishment of the information society in the Republic of Azerbaijan, creation of electronic government, provision of information security, etc. have been set in particular [2, p. 37].

Currently, the "Electronic Government" portal (www.e-gov.az) is active in our Republic, and the attention of the population to its activity is increasing day by day. As planned, all central executive authorities are connected to this portal. About 500 electronic services are provided to our citizens by these institutions. All state institutions and central executive authorities have joined this process and begun to provide "e-services" more widely. In general, the electronic state creates new opportunities for the development of democracy. It is based on the capabilities of information communication technologies that provide mutual information communication between the population and civil society institutions and the authorities. The electronic state forms a system of interaction between citizens, civil society and business structures, and executive power structures through the Internet. The application of information communication technologies to government activities in different countries, the transparency, and availability of state information, the principle of feedback between the population and authorities, the state's responsibility for the decisions made, etc. such issues are the main features characterizing the electronic state [3, p. 208].

As a whole, the national legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan envisages giving special priority status to human rights. Here we are talking about "recognition, observance, and protection of human and civil rights and freedoms". This issue is also known as the obligation of the state. The Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan defines a necessary rule of conduct for the state in accordance with the interests of the people living in its territory. Based on the

Fundamental Law of the country, it can be argued that the functional purpose of fulfilling the state's obligations in the field of human rights is to create the necessary (political, legal, economic, etc.) conditions for ensuring universally recognized human rights standards.

On the one hand, the national characteristics of the state-legal regulation of relations between the state and the individual are related to historical and cultural traditions and the resources that the state currently possesses. On the other hand, in accordance with Articles 10, 12, 71, and 148 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, international human rights act as a limiting factor of state sovereignty and require the realization of the rights and freedoms declared in the Constitution (their implementation). In other words, it requires "good management".

Thus, summarizing what has been mentioned, it can be concluded that although the ways and characteristics of improving public administration and legislation based on good governance law differ from state to state, the general principles are the same. And these general beginnings derive from the very nature of good governance law itself. In the practice of the Republic of Azerbaijan, enough work has been done in this direction at the international and national levels and it has covered all spheres of power. In order to solve the current problems, the negotiations conducted by our state with international organizations should be highly appreciated.

As for the interaction between the right to good governance and children's rights, as a clear example of the consideration of international standards on children's rights in the Republic of Azerbaijan and the inclusion of them in the national legislation, the additions to Article 17 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan with the March 18, 2009 referendum can be noted. Thus, the article includes the provision of state protection to children who are deprived of the protection and care of their parents and guardians. In addition, in the added clauses, the involvement of children in work that endangers their lives, health, and moral development, and specifically the employment of children under the age of 15, is directly mentioned.

One of the forms of realization of international legal obligations regarding children's rights in the Republic of Azerbaijan is a close cooperation with international organizations engaged in the protection of children's rights. A clear example of such cooperation is the high level of cooperation between the Republic of Azerbaijan and UNICEF. In order to strengthen the activities and programs in the field of children's health, development and protection as necessary, this cooperation serves to ensure the implementation of programs on providing financial assistance, sending goods and products, providing education and counseling, meeting the urgent, long-term and current needs of children, protecting the health and nutrition of mothers and children, providing services in

the field of water supply, general education and protection of women.

The 1989 UN Convention on the Rights of the Child can be mentioned among the international conventions that the Republic of Azerbaijan supported in the first years of its independence. The Republic of Azerbaijan joined this Convention in 1992, and in 2002, the I and II additional protocols of that Convention. The main normative-legal act in the direction of protection of children's rights in our republic is the Law on Children's Rights dated May 19, 1998. This Law was prepared in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the 1989 UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, and other international legal norms in the relevant sphere, and it defines the rights and freedoms of children in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the main principles of the state policy related to children, the functions of state bodies and various legal and natural persons operating in the sphere of child protection.

The declaration of 2009 as the "Year of the Child" by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated December 22, 2008, should be regarded as the beginning of a new stage in the direction of the protection of their rights and freedoms. After this event, positive changes were made in the implementation of children's rights such as education and financial security, especially, necessary changes were made in the functions of relevant state bodies to implement measures to improve the material and moral-psychological condition of children in need of care. Later, with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated May 8, 2012, the Rule of State Control over the Implementation of Children's Rights was approved. This document is an indicator that the state plays an important role in the protection of children's rights in our Republic. The main goal of state supervision is to protect the rights and interests of children as determined by the legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan, to create normal conditions for the realization of children's rights, and to prevent situations that hinder the realization of children's rights. In addition, within the framework of cooperation with UNICEF, issues of juvenile justice development were also identified. State control in the Republic of Azerbaijan is carried out by the following state bodies: the State Committee for Family, Women and Children's Issues, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population, the Ministry of Youth and Sports, commissions for the protection of minors' affairs and rights, and guardianship bodies of local executive authorities. Besides, on January 15, 2013, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan approved the Regulation on the organization and management of the electronic information bank on the implementation of children's rights. This system was created for the purpose of state control over the implementation of children's rights and the organization of flexible solutions to children's problems by state bodies [6, p. 23-25].

As it can be seen, in the Republic of Azerbaijan, mutual activities in the direction of ensuring the right to good governance and children's rights were carried out in several directions: ensuring human rights as a whole; establishing the right to good governance in domestic legislation; ensuring the right to good governance for children's rights; coordinating the activities of state bodies on ensuring the right to good governance; implementation of cooperation within the framework of international organizations and international agreements on the development of good governance law; implementation of relevant improvements and developments in this area.

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